

Third order Semi-Canonical Nonlinear Differential Equations with Deviating Arguments: Oscillation via Canonical Transform

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Abstract. This paper presents some new results on the oscillatory and asymptotic behavior of solutions of the third-order nonlinear unstable type semi-canonical differential equation with deviating arguments of the form

$$(a_2(\ell)(a_1(\ell)y'(\ell)))' = p(\ell)y^\mu(\zeta(\ell)) + q(\ell)y^\lambda(v(\ell)), \ell \geq \ell_0$$

(E)

Oscillatory conditions are obtained by converting the semi-canonical type into the canonical type and then using comparison with first-order functional differential equations. Examples are provided to illustrate the novelty and superiorities over already known results.

Keywords: Third-order, semi-canonical, deviating arguments, canonical transform, oscillation.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper is concerned with oscillatory and asymptotic behavior of solutions of the third order nonlinear unstable type semi-canonical functional differential equations of the form

$$(a_2(\ell)(a_1(\ell)y'(\ell)))' = p(\ell)y^\mu(\zeta(\ell)) + q(\ell)y^\lambda(v(\ell)), \ell \geq \ell_0$$

(E)

where the following conditions are always assumed to hold:

- (i) λ and μ are ratios of odd positive integers;
- (ii) $a_1(\ell), a_2(\ell), p(\ell), q(\ell) \in \mathbb{C}([\ell_0, \infty), (0, \infty))$;
- (iii) $\zeta(\ell), v(\ell) \in \mathbb{C}^1([\ell_0, \infty, \mathcal{R}), \zeta(\ell) > \ell, v(\ell) < \ell, v'(\ell) \geq 0, \zeta'(\ell) \geq 0$ and $\lim_{\ell \rightarrow \infty} v(\ell) = \infty$, for all $\ell \geq \ell_0$
- (iv) The equation (E) is in semi – canonical form;

$$A_2(\ell_0) = \int_{\ell_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{a_2(s)} ds < \infty \text{ and } \int_{\ell_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{a_1(s)} ds = \infty, \quad (1.1)$$

$$A_1(\ell_0) = \int_{\ell_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{a_1(s)} ds < \infty \text{ and } \int_{\ell_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{a_2(s)} ds = \infty, \quad (1.2)$$

By a solution of (E), we understand a function $y(\ell) \in \mathbb{C}([\mathcal{T}_y, \infty))$, $\mathcal{T}_y \geq \ell_0$, $a_1(\ell)y'(\ell), a_2(\ell)(a_1(\ell)y'(\ell))'$

are continuously differentiable and satisfy equation (E) on $([\mathcal{T}_y, \infty))$. We consider only those solutions $y(\ell)$ of (E) which satisfy $\sup \{|y(\ell)|; \ell \geq \mathcal{T}\} > 0$ for all $\mathcal{T} \geq \mathcal{T}_y$. A solution of equation (E) is called oscillatory if it has arbitrarily large zeros on $([\mathcal{T}_y, \infty)$; otherwise, it is non oscillatory.

Determining the oscillatory and asymptotic behavior of solutions of different classes of functional differential equations received great interest of many researchers, see, for example, [1]-[22] and the references cited therein. A large amount of significant oscillation results has been collected in several monographs, see, e.g., [2], [13], [19], [22]. This interest is due to the fact that functional differential equations are deemed to be adequate in modeling of numerous processes in all areas of science and technology. It is trustworthy to mention the use of third-order differential equations specifically in the study of an entry-flow phenomenon in a problem of hydrodynamics,

or of the propagation of electrical pulses in the nerve of a squid approximated by the famous Nagumo's equation [22].

In [18], the authors considered the following equation

$$(b(t)(a(t)x'(t)))' = q(t)x(t) = 0$$

when it is in canonical form, that is,

$$\int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{b(s)} ds = \infty, \int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{a(s)} ds = \infty,$$

and shown that there always exists a positive strongly increasing solution.

In [5], the authors investigated oscillation and property B for the following advanced type equation

$$(b(t)(a(t)x'(t)))' = q(t)x(\sigma(t)) = 0$$

when it is in canonical form.

In [15], the authors studied the oscillation of all solutions of third-order nonlinear functional differential equations of the form

$$(a(t)(x''(t))^\alpha)' = q(t)f(x(g(t))) + p(t)h(x(\sigma(t)))$$

with both canonical and semi-canonical cases.

In [25], the authors obtained oscillation and asymptotic behavior of solutions of canonical type neutral differential equations of the form

$$[a(t)[((x(t) + c(t)x(\delta(t))))' \gamma]' = q(t)x^\alpha(\tau(t)) + p(t)x^\beta(\sigma(t))$$

using comparison theorems. For more results concerning the oscillatory and asymptotic behavior of solutions of third-order functional differential equations related to equation (E) can be found in [1], [3], [4], [22] and the references cited therein.

From the review of literature one can see that only few results reported on the oscillatory and asymptotic behavior of solutions of equations similar to (E) and that to for the canonical case. Therefore, our objective in this paper is to establish criteria for all solutions of equation (E) to be oscillatory and this will be developed by transforming the equation (E) into the canonical form. Consequently, our results are new and extended the earlier ones in [1], [10], [14], [15], [21], [25]. Examples are presented to illustrate the importance and novelty of the main results.

2. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

The following notations are used to simplify our results:

$$A_1(\ell) = \int_{\ell}^{\infty} \frac{1}{a_1(s)} ds \quad A_2(\ell) = \int_{\ell}^{\infty} \frac{1}{a_2(s)} ds \quad F_1(\ell) = \int_{\rho(\ell)}^{\varsigma(\ell)} \frac{1}{b_1(u)} du$$

$$F_2(\ell) = Q_1(\ell)F_1^\mu(\ell) \quad F_3(\ell) = F_2(\ell) \left(\int_{\theta(\ell)}^{\rho(\ell)} \frac{1}{b_2(u)} du \right)^\mu, \quad \eta_1(\ell) = Q_2(\ell) \left(\int_{\ell_1}^{\nu(\ell)} \frac{1}{b_1(s)} ds \right)^\lambda$$

$$\eta_2(\ell) = \eta_1(\ell) \left(\int_{\nu(\ell)}^{\xi(\ell)} \frac{1}{b_2(s)} ds \right)^\lambda, \quad \text{where } \ell_1 \geq \ell_0 \text{ is sufficiently large.}$$

Next, we derive canonical form of equation (E) when (1.1) or (1.2) holds. To start with, let us state a characterization of possible non oscillatory solutions of (E) when (1.1) holds.

Lemma 2.1. Assume that $y(\ell)$ is an eventually positive solution of (E) then there exists a $\ell_1 \geq \ell_0$ such that for $\ell_1 \geq \ell_0$, for $\ell \geq \ell_1$, the function $y(\ell)$ satisfies one of the following three possibilities:

$$\begin{aligned} (B_0): & y(\ell) > 0, y'(\ell) < 0, (a_1(\ell)y'(\ell))' > 0, (a_2(\ell)(a_1(\ell)y'(\ell))')' \geq 0 \\ (B_1): & y(\ell) > 0, y'(\ell) > 0, (a_1(\ell)y'(\ell))' > 0, (a_2(\ell)(a_1(\ell)y'(\ell))')' \geq 0 \\ (B_2): & y(\ell) > 0, y'(\ell) > 0, (a_1(\ell)y'(\ell))' < 0, (a_2(\ell)(a_1(\ell)y'(\ell))')' \geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

The above lemma can be found in [25]. Further, the set of nonoscillatory solutions of (E) satisfies three types when case (1.2) holds. Hence to find the oscillation criteria for the equation (E), we have to eliminate these three types of nonoscillatory solutions. In the following using a simple condition, we transform the equation (E) into canonical form, which reduced the three possible cases into two. So, this significantly simplifies our investigation to find criteria for the oscillation of all solutions of (E) by eliminating these two types of nonoscillatory solutions. We begin with the following theorem.

Theorem 2.2. Let (1.1) hold. If

$$\int_{\ell_0}^{\infty} \frac{A_2(s)}{a_1(s)} ds = \infty \quad (2.1)$$

then the canonical form of the semi-canonical operator is

$$\left(a_2(\ell)(a_1(\ell)y'(\ell))' \right)' = \frac{1}{A_2(\ell)} (b_2(\ell)(b_1(\ell)z'(\ell))')' \quad (2.2)$$

where $z(\ell) = y(\ell)$, $b_1(\ell) = \frac{a_1(\ell)}{A_2(\ell)}$, $b_2(\ell) = a_2(\ell)A_2^2(\ell)$.

Proof. The details are omitted because the proof of the theorem is very similar to Theorem 2.1 in [24]. This ends the proof.

Theorem 2.3. Let (1.2) hold. If

$$\int_{\ell_0}^{\infty} \frac{A_1(s)}{a_2(s)} ds = \infty \quad (2.3)$$

then the canonical form of the semi-canonical operator is

$$\left(a_2(\ell)(a_1(\ell)y'(\ell))' \right)' = (c_2(\ell)(c_1(\ell)z'(\ell))')' \quad (2.4)$$

where $z(\ell) = \frac{y(\ell)}{A_1(\ell)}$, $c_1(\ell) = a_1(\ell)A_1^2(\ell)$, $c_2(\ell) = \frac{a_2(\ell)}{A_1(\ell)}$.

Proof. The details are omitted because the proof is similar to Theorem 2.1 in [23]. This ends the proof.

By combining Theorem 2.1 and Theorem 2.2, we have the following theorem.

Theorem 2.4. For the case (1.1) with (2.1) and for the case (1.2) with (2.3) holds, then the canonical form of the equation (E) is

$$\left(b_2(\ell)(b_1(\ell)z'(\ell))' \right)' = Q_1(\ell)z^\mu(\zeta(\ell)) + Q_2(\ell)z^\lambda(\nu(\ell)) \quad \text{for } \ell \geq \ell_0 \geq 0 \quad (E_c)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} b_1(\ell) &= \begin{cases} \frac{a_1(\ell)}{A_2(\ell)} & \text{if (1.1) holds} \\ a_1(\ell)A_1^2(\ell) & \text{if (1.2) holds} \end{cases} \\ b_2(\ell) &= \begin{cases} a_2(\ell)A_2^2(\ell) & \text{if (1.1) holds} \\ \frac{a_2(\ell)}{A_1(\ell)} & \text{if (1.2) holds} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

$$Q_1(\ell) = \begin{cases} p(\ell)A_2(\ell) & \text{if (1.1) holds} \\ p(\ell)A_1(\zeta(\ell)) & \text{if (1.2) holds} \end{cases}$$

$$Q_2(\ell) = \begin{cases} q(\ell)A_2(\ell) & \text{if (1.1) holds} \\ q(\ell)A_1(v(\ell)) & \text{if (1.2) holds} \end{cases}$$

$$z(\ell) = \begin{cases} y(\ell) & \text{if (1.1) holds} \\ \frac{y(\ell)}{A_1(\ell)} & \text{if (1.2) holds} \end{cases}$$

Corollary 2.5. Let the condition (2.1) or (2.3) holds, then the semi-canonical equation (E) possess a solution $y(\ell)$ if and only if the canonical equation (E_c) has the solution $z(\ell)$.

Corollary 2.6. Let the condition (2.1) and (2.3) holds, then the semi - canonical equation (E) has an eventually positive solution $y(\ell)$ if and only if canonical equation (E_c) of $z(\ell)$. has an eventually positive solution.

From the above corollary, it is clear that the investigation of the oscillation of (E) is reduced to that of (E_c) and therefore, if $y(\ell)$ is an eventually positive solution of (E) then by the Kiguradze [17] lemma, the function $z(\ell)$ satisfies one of the following two cases:

$$(B_1^*): z(\ell) > 0, z'(\ell) > 0, (b_1(\ell)z'(\ell))' > 0, (b_2(\ell)(b_1(\ell)z'(\ell))')' \geq 0$$

$$(B_2^*): z(\ell) > 0, z'(\ell) > 0, (b_1(\ell)z'(\ell))' < 0, (b_2(\ell)(b_1(\ell)z'(\ell))')' \geq 0$$

3. OSCILLATION OF EQUATION (E)

In this section, we present oscillation criteria of (E) using the equation (E_c) and comparison with first-order functional differential equations. In the remaining part of the paper, we assume without further mention that the conditions (1.1) and (2.1) ((1.2) and (2.3)) are hold. We begin with the following theorem.

Theorem 3.1. Assume that there exist non-decreasing functions $\xi(\ell), \rho(\ell), \theta(\ell) \in C^1([t_0, \infty), \mathfrak{R})$ such that $v(\ell) < \xi(\ell) < \ell$ and $\zeta(\ell) > \rho(\ell) > \theta(\ell) > \ell$ for $\ell \geq \ell_0$. If the advanced first-order differential equation

$$w'(\ell) - F_3(\ell)w^\mu(\theta(\ell)) = 0$$

(3.1)

and the first-order delay differential equation

$$x'(\ell) + \eta_2(\ell)x^\lambda(\xi(\ell)) = 0$$

(3.2)

are oscillatory, then the equation (E) is oscillatory.

Proof. Assume the contrary that $y(\ell)$ is an eventually positive solution of (E). Then by Corollary 2.4 and Corollary 2.5, the corresponding function $z(\ell)$ is also positive solution of (E_c) and hence $z \in (B_1^*)$ or (B_2^*) for $\ell \geq \ell_1 \geq \ell_0$. Choose $\ell \geq \ell_1 \geq \ell_0$ so that $z(\ell) > 0, z(v(\ell)) > 0, z(\zeta(\ell)) > 0, \text{ for } \ell \geq \ell_1$.

First, assume that $z \in (B_1^*)$: For $\ell \geq s \geq \ell_1$, we have

$$z(\ell) - z(s) = \int_s^\ell \frac{b_1(u)z'(u)}{b_1(u)} du,$$

hence

$$z(\ell) \geq (b_1(s)z'(s)) \int_s^\ell \frac{1}{b_1(u)} du \quad (3.3)$$

Replacing ℓ and s in (3.3) by $\zeta(\ell)$ and $\rho(\ell)$ respectively, we get

$$z(\zeta(\ell)) \geq F_1(\ell)b_1(\rho(\ell))z'(\rho(\ell)) \text{ for } \ell \geq \ell_2 \geq \ell_1 \quad (3.4)$$

Substituting (3.4) in (E_c), we get

$$(3.5) \quad (b_2(\ell)(b_1(\ell)z'(\ell)))' \geq Q_1(\ell)F_1^\mu(\ell)(b_1(\rho(\ell))z'(\rho(\ell)))^\mu$$

Let $\delta(\ell) = b_1(\ell)z'(\ell)$, then (3.5) becomes

$$(3.6) \quad (b_2(\ell)\delta'(\ell))' = F_2(\ell)\delta^\mu(\rho(\ell)) \text{ for } \ell \geq \ell_2$$

Once again for $\ell \geq s \geq \ell_2$, we have

$$\delta(\ell) - \delta(s) = \int_s^\ell \frac{b_2(u)\delta'(u)}{b_2(u)} du$$

and hence we have

$$\delta(\ell) \geq b_2(s)\delta'(s) \int_s^\ell \frac{1}{b_2(u)} du \quad (3.7)$$

Replacing ℓ and s by $\rho(\ell)$ and $\theta(\ell)$, respectively, we get

$$\delta(\rho(\ell)) \geq b_2(\theta(\ell))\delta'(\theta(\ell)) \int_{\theta(\ell)}^{\rho(\ell)} \frac{1}{b_2(u)} du \text{ for } \ell \geq \ell_3 \geq \ell_2 \quad (3.8)$$

Let $w(\ell) = b_2(\ell)\delta'(\ell)$. Using (3.8) in (3.6) yields

$$(3.9) \quad w'(\ell) - F_3(\ell)w^\mu(\theta(\ell)) \geq 0$$

In view of Lemma 1 in [1], it follows that the corresponding differential equation (3.1) also has a positive solution, which is a contradiction.

Next, assume that $z \in (B_2^*)$: For $\ell_1 \geq \ell_0$, we see that

$$z(\ell) \geq b_1(\ell)z'(\ell) \int_{\ell_1}^\ell \frac{1}{b_1(u)} du,$$

and hence

$$z(v(\ell)) \geq b_1(v(\ell))z'(v(\ell)) \int_{\ell_1}^{v(\ell)} \frac{1}{b_1(u)} du$$

Using the last inequality in equation (E_c), we have

$$(3.10) \quad (b_2(\ell)(b_1(\ell)z'(\ell)))' \geq \eta_1(\ell)(b_1(v(\ell))z'(v(\ell)))^\lambda$$

Let $b_1(\ell)z'(\ell) = \varphi(\ell)$, then

$$(3.11) \quad (b_2(\ell)\varphi'(\ell))' \geq \eta_1(v(\ell))\varphi^\lambda(v(\ell))$$

Now for $\ell \geq s \geq \ell_1$, we have

$$\varphi(s) - \varphi(\ell) = \int_s^\ell -\varphi'(u) du$$

Or

$$\varphi(s) \geq - \int_s^\ell \frac{b_2(u)\varphi'(u)}{b_2(u)} du \geq -b_2(\ell)\varphi'(\ell) \int_s^\ell \frac{1}{b_2(u)} du$$

Replacing s and ℓ by $v(\ell)$ and $\xi(\ell)$, respectively, we have

$$\varphi(v(\ell)) \geq -b_2(\xi(\ell))\varphi'(\xi(\ell)) \int_{v(\ell)}^{\xi(\ell)} \frac{1}{b_2(u)} du \quad (3.12)$$

Letting $b_2(\ell)\varphi'(\ell) = x(\ell)$ and using (3.12) in (3.11), we get

$$x'(\ell) + \eta_2(\ell)x^\lambda(\xi(\ell)) \leq 0 \quad (3.13)$$

Integrating equation (3.13) from ℓ to T and letting T tends to ∞ , we get

$$x(\ell) \geq \int_{\ell}^{\infty} \eta_2(s) (x^\lambda(\xi(s))) ds.$$

The function $x(\ell)$ is strictly decreasing on $[\ell_1, \infty)$ and therefore by Theorem 1 of [20], we see that there exists a positive solution $x(\ell)$ of equation (3.2) such that $\lim_{\ell \rightarrow \infty} x(\ell) = 0$ which is a contradiction. Hence equation (E_c) is oscillatory and by the oscillation preserving transformation, we conclude that (E) is also oscillatory. This completes the proof.

Theorem 3.2. Assume that there exist nondecreasing function $\alpha(\ell) \in \mathbb{C}^1([\ell_0, \infty), \mathfrak{R})$ such that

$$\alpha(\ell) < \ell \text{ and } \beta(\ell) = \varsigma(\alpha(\ell)) > \ell \text{ for } \ell \geq \ell_0 \quad (3.14)$$

If the first-order advanced differential equations

$$\mathcal{W}'(\ell) - \left(\frac{1}{b_1} \int_{\alpha(\ell)}^{\ell} \frac{1}{b_2(s)} \int_{\alpha(s)}^s Q_1(u) du ds \right) \mathcal{W}^\mu(\beta(\ell)) = 0 \quad (3.15)$$

and

$$\varrho'(\ell) - \left(\frac{1}{b_1} \int_{\ell}^{\infty} \frac{1}{b_2(s)} \int_s^{\infty} Q_1(u) du ds \right) \varrho^\mu(\varsigma(\ell)) = 0 \quad (3.16)$$

are oscillatory, then the equation (E) is oscillatory.

Proof. Assume the contrary that $y(\ell)$ is an eventually positive solution of (E). Then proceeding as in Theorem 3.1, we see that the corresponding function $z(\ell)$ is also positive solution of (E_c) and hence $z \in (B_1^*)$ or (B_2^*) for $\ell \geq \ell_1 \geq \ell_0$.

First, assume that $z \in (B_1^*)$: It follows from (E_c) that

$$(b_2(\ell)(b_1(\ell)z'(\ell)))' \geq Q_1(\ell)z^\mu(\varsigma(\ell))$$

Integrating from $\alpha(\ell)$ to ℓ , we get

$$(b_1(\ell)z'(\ell))' \geq \frac{z^\mu(\varsigma(\alpha(\ell)))}{b_2(\ell)} \int_{\alpha(\ell)}^{\ell} Q_1(s) ds$$

Again integrating from $\alpha(\ell)$ to ℓ , yields

$$z'(\ell) \geq \frac{z^\mu(\beta(\ell))}{b_1(\ell)} \int_{\alpha(\ell)}^{\ell} \frac{1}{b_2(s)} \left(\int_{\alpha(s)}^s Q_1(u) du \right) ds$$

Hence, $z(\ell)$ is a positive solution of the advanced differential inequality

$$z'(\ell) - \left(\frac{1}{b_1(\ell)} \int_{\alpha(\ell)}^{\ell} \frac{1}{b_2(s)} \left(\int_{\alpha(s)}^s Q_1(u) du \right) ds \right) z^\mu(\beta(\ell)) \geq 0$$

But by Lemma 1 of [1], we conclude that the corresponding differential equation (3.15) also has a positive solution, which is a contradiction.

Next, assume that $z \in (B_2^*)$: Integrating (E_c) from ℓ to ∞ . We obtain

$$-b_2(\ell)(b_1(\ell)z'(\ell))' \geq \int_{\ell}^{\infty} Q_1(s) z^{\mu}(\zeta(s)) ds \geq z^{\mu}(\zeta(\ell)) \int_{\ell}^{\infty} Q_1(s) ds$$

Divide the last inequality by $b_2(\ell)$ and then integrating from ℓ to ∞ , one gets

$$z'(\ell) \geq \frac{1}{b_1(\ell)} \int_{\ell}^{\infty} \frac{z^{\mu}(\zeta(s))}{b_2(s)} \int_{s}^{\infty} Q_1(u) du ds \geq \frac{z^{\mu}(\zeta(\ell))}{b_1(\ell)} \int_{\ell}^{\infty} \frac{1}{b_2(s)} \int_{s}^{\infty} Q_1(u) du ds$$

consequently, $z(\ell)$ is a positive solution of the advanced differential inequality

$$z'(\ell) - \left(\frac{1}{b_1(\ell)} \int_{\ell}^{\infty} \frac{1}{b_2(s)} \int_{s}^{\infty} Q_1(u) du ds \right) z^{\mu}(\zeta(\ell)) \geq 0.$$

By Lemma 1 of [1], we deduce that there exists a positive solution of (3.16), which is again a contradiction. This ends the proof.

Remark 3.3. Note that from the proof of Theorem 3.2, that if

$$\int_{\ell_0}^{\infty} Q_1(\ell) d\ell = \infty \quad \text{or} \quad \int_{\ell_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{b_2(\ell)} \int_{\ell}^{\infty} Q_1(s) ds d\ell = \infty,$$

then a nonoscillatory solution $z(\ell)$ of (E_c) cannot satisfy the case (B_2^*) .

In the following, we present explicit criteria for the oscillation of all solutions of (E) for the different values of μ and λ .

Corollary 3.4. Let $\mu = 1$ and $\lambda = 1$. Assume that there exist nondecreasing functions $\xi(\ell), \rho(\ell), \theta(\ell) \in \mathbb{C}^{\infty}([\ell_0, \infty), \mathbb{R})$, such that

$$(3.17) \quad v(\ell) < \xi(\ell) < \ell, \quad \ell \geq \ell_0$$

and

$$(3.18) \quad \varsigma(\ell) > \rho(\ell) > \theta(\ell) > \ell, \quad \ell \geq \ell_0$$

If

$$\liminf_{\ell \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\ell}^{\theta(\ell)} F_3(s) ds > \frac{1}{e} \quad (3.19)$$

and

$$\liminf_{\ell \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\xi(\ell)}^{\ell} \eta_2(s) ds > \frac{1}{e} \quad (3.20)$$

then equation (E) is oscillatory.

Proof. In view of well-known results in [19], we see that the equations (3.1) and (3.2) are oscillatory under the conditions (3.19) and (3.20) respectively. The conclusion now follows from Theorem 3.1. This ends the proof.

Corollary 3.5. Let conditions (3.17) and (3.18) holds and let $\mu = 1$ and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$. If condition (3.19) and

$$\int_{\ell_0}^{\infty} \eta_2(\ell) d\ell = \infty \quad (3.21)$$

holds, then equation (E) is oscillatory.

Proof. In view of well-known results in [19] and [11], we see that the equation (3.1) and (3.2) are oscillatory under the conditions (3.19) and (3.21) respectively. The conclusion now follows from Theorem 3.1. This ends the proof.

Corollary 3.6. Let conditions (3.17) and (3.18) holds and let $\mu > 1$ and $\lambda = 1$. If condition (3.20) and

$$\int_{\ell_1}^{\infty} F_3(\ell) d\ell = \infty$$

(3.22)

holds, then equation (E) is oscillatory.

Proof. Proceeding as in Theorem 3.1, we arrive at (3.1). Since $\mathcal{W}(\ell)$ is increasing and $\theta(\ell) > \ell$, we have from (3.1) that

$$\frac{\mathcal{W}'(\ell)}{\mathcal{W}^{\mu}(\ell)} > F_3(\ell).$$

Integrating the last inequality from ℓ_1 to ∞ , we obtain

$$\frac{1}{(\mu - 1)\mathcal{W}^{\mu-1}(\ell_1)} \geq \int_{\ell_1}^{\infty} F_3(s) ds$$

which contradicts (3.22). Therefore, equation (3.1) is oscillatory and by condition (3.20), the equation (3.2) is oscillatory. Now, the conclusion follows from Theorem 3.1. This ends the proof.

Corollary 3.7. Let conditions (3.17) and (3.18) holds and let $\mu > 1$ and $\lambda \in (0,1)$. If conditions (3.21) and (3.22) holds, then equation (E) is oscillatory.

Proof. The proof follows from Corollary 3.5 and Corollary 3.6. This completes the proof.

Next, by using Theorem 3.2 instead of Theorem 3.1, we get the following corollaries.

Corollary 3.8. Let condition (3.14) hold and let $\mu > 1$. If

$$\int_{\ell_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{b_1(\ell)} \int_{\alpha(s)}^s \frac{1}{b_2(s_1)} \int_{\alpha(s_1)}^{s_1} Q_1(s_2) ds_2 ds_1 ds = \infty \quad (3.23)$$

and

$$\int_{\ell_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{b_1(\ell)} \int_s^{\infty} \frac{1}{b_2(s_1)} \int_{s_1}^{\infty} Q_1(s_2) ds_2 ds_1 ds = \infty \quad (3.24)$$

then equation (E) is oscillatory.

Proof. The proof follows from Corollary 3.6 and this ends the proof.

Corollary 3.9. Let condition (3.14) hold and let $\mu = 1$. If

$$\liminf_{\ell \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\ell}^{\beta(\ell)} \frac{1}{b_1(s)} \int_{\alpha(s)}^s \frac{1}{b_2(s_1)} \int_{\alpha(s_1)}^{s_1} Q_1(s_2) ds_2 ds_1 ds > \frac{1}{e} \quad (3.25)$$

and

$$\liminf_{\ell \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\ell}^{\alpha(\ell)} \frac{1}{b_1(s)} \int_s^{\infty} \frac{1}{b_2(s_1)} \int_{s_1}^{\infty} Q_1(s_2) ds_2 ds_1 ds > \frac{1}{e} \quad (3.26)$$

then equation (E) is oscillatory.

Proof. In view of well-known results in [19], we see that the equations (3.15) and (3.16) are oscillatory under the conditions (3.25) and (3.26) respectively. Now the conclusion follows from Theorem 3.2. This ends the proof.

4. EXAMPLES

In this section, we present several examples to illustrate the importance and novelty of the main results.

Example 4.1. Consider the third-order semi-canonical functional differential equation

$$(\ell^2 (\frac{1}{\ell} \psi'(\ell)))' = \frac{a}{\ell^2} \psi(2\ell) + \frac{b}{\ell^2} \psi\left(\frac{\ell}{2}\right) \quad (4.1)$$

where $a > 0$ and $b > 0$ are constants. Simple calculation shows that $A_2(\ell) = \frac{1}{\ell}$ and the condition (2.1) holds. Next, $b_1(\ell) = b_2(\ell) = 1$, $Q_1(\ell) = \frac{a}{\ell^3}$ and $Q_2(\ell) = \frac{b}{\ell^3}$.

The transformed equation is

$$z'''(\ell) = \frac{a}{\ell^3} z(2\ell) + \frac{b}{\ell^3} z\left(\frac{\ell}{2}\right), \ell \geq 1,$$

which is in canonical form. Choose $\rho(\ell) = \frac{3}{2}\ell$, $\theta(\ell) = \frac{5}{4}\ell$, so condition $\zeta(\ell) > \rho(\ell) > \theta(\ell) > \ell$ holds. Next, choose $\xi(\ell) = \frac{3}{4}\ell$ so that condition $\nu(\ell) < \xi(\ell) < \ell$ holds. With further conclusion, we see that

$$F_3(\ell) = \frac{a}{8\ell} \text{ and } \eta_2(\ell) = \frac{b}{8\ell}.$$

The conditions (3.19) becomes

$$\liminf_{\ell \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\frac{3}{4}\ell}^{\frac{5}{4}\ell} \frac{a}{8s} ds = \frac{a}{8} \ln \frac{5}{4} > \frac{1}{e},$$

that is, condition (3.19) holds if $a > \frac{8}{e \ln \frac{5}{4}}$.

Next, the condition (3.20) becomes

$$\liminf_{\ell \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\frac{3}{4}\ell}^{\ell} \frac{b}{8s} ds = \frac{b}{8} \ln \frac{4}{3} > \frac{1}{e},$$

that is, condition (3.20) holds if $b > \frac{8}{e \ln \frac{4}{3}}$. By Corollary 3.4, the equation (4.1) is oscillatory if $a > \frac{8}{e \ln \frac{5}{4}}$ and $b > \frac{8}{e \ln \frac{4}{3}}$.

Example 4.2. Consider the third-order semi-canonical functional differential equation

$$\left(\frac{1}{\ell}(\ell^2(y'(\ell)))'\right)' = \frac{a}{\ell^2} y(2\ell) + \frac{b}{\ell^2} y\left(\frac{\ell}{2}\right), \ell \geq 1, \quad (4.2)$$

where $a > 0$ and $b > 0$ are constants. Simple calculations show that $A_1(\ell) = \frac{1}{\ell}$ and condition (2.3) holds. Next, $b_1(\ell) = b_2(\ell) = 1$, $Q_1(\ell) = \frac{a}{2\ell^3}$ and $Q_2(\ell) = \frac{2b}{\ell^3}$.

The transformed equation is

$$z'''(\ell) = \frac{a}{\ell^3} z(2\ell) + \frac{2b}{\ell^3} z\left(\frac{\ell}{2}\right), \ell \geq 1,$$

which is in canonical form.

Choose $\rho(\ell) = \frac{3}{2}\ell$, $\theta(\ell) = \frac{5}{4}\ell$, so condition $\zeta(\ell) > \rho(\ell) > \theta(\ell) > \ell$ holds. Next, choose $\xi(\ell) = \frac{3}{4}\ell$ so that condition $\nu(\ell) < \xi(\ell) < \ell$ holds. With further calculation, we see that

$$F_3(\ell) = \frac{a}{16\ell} \text{ and } \eta_2(\ell) = \frac{b}{4\ell}$$

The conditions (3.19) becomes

$$\liminf_{\ell \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\frac{3}{4}\ell}^{\frac{5}{4}\ell} \frac{a}{16s} ds = \frac{a}{16} \ln \frac{5}{4} > \frac{1}{e},$$

that is, condition (3.19) holds if $a > \frac{16}{e \ln \frac{5}{4}}$. Next, the condition (3.20) becomes

$$\liminf_{\ell \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\frac{3}{4}\ell}^{\ell} \frac{b}{4s} ds = \frac{b}{4} \ln \frac{4}{3} > \frac{1}{e},$$

that is, condition (3.20) holds if $b > \frac{8}{e \ln \frac{4}{3}}$. By Corollary 3.4, the equation (4.2) is oscillatory if $a > \frac{16}{e \ln \frac{5}{4}}$ and $b > \frac{4}{e \ln \frac{4}{3}}$.

Example 4.3. Consider the third-order semi-canonical functional differential equation

$$(\ell^2 \psi''(\ell))' = a \psi^3 \left(\frac{3}{2} \ell \right) + b \psi^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\frac{\ell}{2} \right), \ell \geq 1, \quad (4.3)$$

where $a > 0$ and $b > 0$ are constants. By a simple calculation, we have $A_2(\ell) = \frac{1}{\ell}$ and condition (2.1) holds. Next, $b_1(\ell) = \ell, b_2(\ell) = 1, Q_1(\ell) = \frac{a}{\ell}$ and $Q_2(\ell) = \frac{b}{\ell}$.

The transformed equation is

$$(\ell z'(\ell))'' = \frac{a}{\ell} z^3 \left(\frac{3}{2} \ell \right) + \frac{b}{\ell} z^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\frac{\ell}{2} \right), \ell \geq 1,$$

which is in canonical form. With a further calculation, we see that

$$F_3(\ell) = \frac{a \ell^2}{512} \left(\ln \frac{6}{5} \right)^3 \quad \text{and} \quad \eta_2(\ell) = \left(\frac{\ln \ell / 2}{4} \right)^{1/3} \frac{1}{\ell^{2/3}}.$$

It is easy to see that conditions (3.21) and (3.22) are clearly holds if $a > 0$ and $b > 0$. Hence by Corollary 3.7, equation (4.3) is oscillatory if $a > 0$ and $b > 0$.

Note that the same equation (4.3) is considered in [1] with $a = b = 1$ and it is shown that the equation (4.3) is oscillatory for $a = b = 1$. However, our theorem shown that equation (4.3) is oscillatory for all $a > 0$ and $b > 0$.

Example 4.4. Consider the third-order semi-canonical functional differential equation

$$(\ell^2 \psi'(\ell))'' = a \ell \psi^3 \left(\frac{3}{2} \ell \right) + b \ell^d \psi^\lambda \left(\frac{\ell}{2} \right), \ell \geq 1, \quad (4.4)$$

where $a > 0, d \in \mathbb{R}$ and $b > 0$. By a simple calculation, we see that $A_1(\ell) = \frac{1}{\ell}$ and condition (2.3) holds.

Further, $b_1(\ell) = 1, b_2(\ell) = \ell, Q_1(\ell) = \frac{2a}{3}$ and $Q_2(\ell) = \frac{2b \ell^d}{\ell}$. The transformed equation is

$$(\ell z''(\ell))' = \frac{2a}{3} z^3 \left(\frac{3}{2} \ell \right) + \frac{2b \ell^d}{\ell} z^\lambda \left(\frac{\ell}{2} \right), \ell \geq 1,$$

which is in canonical form. Choose $\alpha(\ell) = \frac{5}{6} \ell$ then condition (3.14) hold. The condition (3.23) after simplification becomes

$$\int_1^\infty \int_{\frac{5s}{6}}^s \frac{1}{s_1} \int_{\frac{5s_1}{6}}^{s_1} \frac{2a}{3} ds_2 ds_1 ds = \frac{2a}{18} \int_1^\infty \frac{s_1}{6} ds = \infty$$

that is, condition (3.23) holds if $a > 0$. The condition (3.24) after simplification becomes

$$\frac{2a}{3} \int_1^\infty \int_s^\infty \frac{1}{s_1} \int_{s_1}^\infty ds_2 ds_1 ds = \infty$$

that is, condition (3.24) holds if $a > 0$. Hence, by Corollary 3.8, we see that equation (4.4) is oscillatory.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper by using simple condition, the semi-canonical equation (E) transformed into canonical type equation which reduced the number of classes of nonoscillatory solutions into two instead of three. This significantly simplifies the examination of oscillation of the studied equation (E). The oscillation criteria are obtained via comparison with first-order functional differential equations. Moreover, four examples are given to

show the importance and novelty of our results. The results already known cannot be applied to our examples because $a_1(t) \neq 1$ or condition (1.2) holds. Hence the results obtained here are new and further contribution to the oscillation theory of functional differential equations with mixed type.

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